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Effect of Row Arrangement and Integrated Nutrient Management on the Growth of Aromatic Fine Rice cv. BRRI dhan 34

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted at the Agronomy Field Laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, during the period from June to December 2014 to study the growth of aromatic fine rice (cv. BRRI dhan34) as affected by row arrangement and integrated nutrient management. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications consisting of the following treatments- a) three row arrangement namely, (i) single row, (ii) double row, (iii) triple row; and b) six nutrient managements viz. (i) control (no manures and fertilizers), (ii) recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers (i.e 150, 100, 70, 60 and 10 kg Urea, TSP, MoP, Gypsum and ZnSO₄ respectively ha⁻¹), (iii) 50% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹, (iv) 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹, (v) 50% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha⁻¹ and (vi) 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha⁻¹. The data analysis results showed that double row arrangement produced the tallest plant (117.8 cm) at 85 DAT, the highest number of total tillers hill⁻¹ (15.56) and the highest leaf area index (5.75) at 65 DAT, the highest total dry matter hill⁻¹ (35.88 g) at 85 DAT and the highest crop growth rate (41.65 g m⁻² day⁻¹) at 65-85 DAT. The application of 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹ showed superiority in terms of having highest plant height (119.67 cm), highest number of total tillers hill⁻¹ (14.89), highest leaf area index (6.05), highest total dry matter (39.94 g) and highest crop growth rate (41.85 g m⁻² day⁻¹). The treatment control gave the lowest values for the same parameters. Therefore, double row arrangement combined with 75% recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹ and 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha⁻¹ appeared as the promising practice in aromatic fine rice cv. BRRI dhan34 cultivation in terms of growth and yield.

Keywords

Aromatic fine rice, row arrangement, nutrient management, plant growth, yield.

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) serves as the main staple food for more than half of the world's population. The major percent of the world's rice is produced and consumed in Asian countries including Bangladesh [1]. Nearly 75 percent of the cropped area of Bangladesh is used for rice cultivation with annual production of 34.71 million ton from 11.42 million hectare of land [2]. The geographic and agro-ecological conditions of Bangladesh are suitable for growing rice year-round. The three main rice cropping seasons of Bangladesh are: (i) the Aus rice (March to June), (ii) the Transplant *Aman* (T. *Aman*) rice (mid-June to mid-November), and (iii) the Boro rice (January to mid-May). In recent years, aromatic rice known as fragrant rice has been introduced and estimated to account for 15-18% of the rice trade procuring the highest prices on the world market [3]. Earlier aromatic rice was only popular in Southeast Asia but nowadays its popularity spread to United States and Europe [4]. Growing demand of aromatic rice in both local and international markets with lucrative prices has encouraged farmers to increase their aromatic rice cultivation in recent years. Nowadays, farmers are more dependent on high-yielding automatic rice varieties because indigenous varieties can yield 187-299 kilograms per 0.33 acre of land, while the high-yielding ones produce 448-821 kilograms per 0.33 acre. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI) has released eight fine and aromatic rice varieties and BRRI-dhan 34 is the most cultivated varieties [5]. Yield of crops changes because of agronomic practices and growing conditions, for example, agroclimatic conditions, distinctive dates of planting and planting density, seed treatment, nutrient management and so forth [6, 7, 8]. The planting density of rice is the most prominent and has significant effects on the growth, development, and yield of rice in field conditions. Optimum row arrangement is the most important factor ensures plants grow properly through adequate utilization of moisture, light, spacing, and nutrients [6]. Closer spacing increased competition among the crops more severely for nutrients, air, and light as a result in weaker crops grow and decrease the production of rice. Previous study showed that the double row shows better performance over single and triple row arrangements. [9, 10]. Transplant *Aman* rice can be grown in both single and double row arrangement in order to obtain proper vegetative growth and yield [11]. Although the agroclimatic conditions of Bangladesh are favorable for growing rice year-round, the national average yield of rice is rather lower (2.876 t ha⁻¹) than other rice growing countries [2]. The main reason for this low yield is lack of information on using fertilizers or nutrients especially organic fertilizer like cow dung, poultry manure and/or their integration with inorganic fertilizers. Some studies showed that nutrient mining, depletion of soil organic matter, reduction in soil aggregates etc. have been identified as reasons for yield stagnation or decline in the productivity of crops [12]. Among the nutrient management practices, application of organic fertilizers such as cowdung, poultry manure, green manure and Vermicompost are more profitable, economic and environmental friendly than inorganic fertilizers to avoid attack of insects, pests and diseases. Organic manures play a key role in rice production through improving soil resource from degradation [13] but required in larger amounts compared to inorganic fertilizers. Effects of organic manures in the vegetative

growth, development and yield of rice have been widely recognized, particularly after the release of modern varieties [14].

The efficient nutrient management increases crop yield and at the same time reduces fertilization cost. There is a lot of research information on specific rice varieties, but a little is documented on comparative study of nutrient management for aromatic fine rice cv. BRRI dhan34. This research work essential to find out suitable row spacing and optimum rate of cow dung and poultry manure in combination with inorganic fertilizers (Urea, TSP, MoP, Gypsum and $ZnSO_4$) and to obtain satisfactory growth of yield components of aromatic fine rice cv. BRRI dhan34.

Materials and method

The research work was conducted at the Agronomy Field laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, during the period from June to December 2014. The experimental site belongs to the Sonatola series of the non-calcareous dark gray floodplain soil under the Old Brahmaputra Floodplain Agro-ecological Zone (AEZ 9). The field was a medium high land with well drained silty-loam texture having pH 6.5, low in organic matter content (1.67%). The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Each of the replication represented a block in the experiment. Each block was divided into 18 unit plots where 18 treatment combinations were allocated at random. There were 54 unit plots in the experiment. The size of unit plot was 4.0 m × 2.5 m. The distances between blocks and plots were 1 m and 75cm, respectively. The experiment comprised- a) three row arrangement namely, (i) single row, (ii) double row, (iii) triple row; and b) six nutrient managements viz. (i) control (no manures and fertilizers), (ii) recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers (i.e 150, 100, 70, 60 and 10 kg Urea, TSP, MoP, Gypsum and $ZnSO_4$ respectively ha^{-1}), (iii) 50% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha^{-1} , (iv) 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha^{-1} , (v) 50% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha^{-1} and (vi) 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha^{-1} . The seeds of fine rice variety BRRI dhan34 were collected from the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Gazipur. The land was puddled with country plough, cleaned and leveled with ladder. Then the sprouted seeds were sown in the nursery beds on 7 July 2014. The land was then puddled thoroughly by repeated ploughing and cross ploughing with a country plough and subsequently leveled by laddering. The field layout was made on 8 August 2014 according to experimental specification immediately after final land preparation. At the time of final land preparation, respective unit plots were amended with organic and inorganic fertilizers according to treatment specification. Urea was applied in three equal splits at final land preparation, 30 days after transplanting (DAT) and 50 DAT. Full dose of triple super phosphate, muriate of potash, gypsum and zinc sulphate were applied at final land preparation as per treatment requirements. Thirty-day old seedlings were

transplanted in the main field as per experimental treatments on 8 August 2014 in the well puddled plot. Three seedlings were transplanted in each hill maintaining single, double and triple row arrangement with 25 cm × 15 cm, 25-10-25 cm × 15 cm, 25-10-10-25 cm × 15cm, spacing respectively. Prior to harvest five hills plot⁻¹ were randomly selected excluding border hills and central 5 m² area from each unit plot for recording data on yield components and yield. The crop was harvested at full maturity on 8 December 2014. Growth parameters which were recorded at 20-day intervals were plant height, number of tillers hill⁻¹, leaf area index (LAI), dry matter production and crop growth rate. Five hills were randomly selected soon after transplanting and marked with bamboo sticks in each plot excluding border rows to record the data on plant height and number of tillers hill⁻¹ at 20-day intervals beginning 25 DAT up to 85 DAT. Plant height (selected five plants) was measured from the ground level to the tip of the longest panicle. Tillers which had at least one leaf visible were counted. It included both productive and non-bearing tillers. Growth parameters viz. Leaf area (cm²), Plant dry matter (g) and Crop growth rate (CGR) (g m⁻² day⁻¹) were measured. For measurement of leaf area and plant dry matter, destructive samples of five randomly selected hills excluding boarder rows were used. Leaf area of five selected plants from each plot was estimated with the help of a leaf area meter and the mean value was recorded. To determine the dry matter yield weight the samples were first air dried for 6 to 8 hours then plants were packed in separate brown paper bag and were oven dried for 72 hours at 70° C. After drying, weight of each sample was recorded. The average data were used to determine the crop growth rate. CGR was calculated using standard formula [15] and CGR expressed by g m⁻² day⁻¹. The collected data were compiled and tabulated in proper form and analyzed statistically using the analysis of variance (ANOVA) technique and mean differences were adjudged by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) [16] using a computer operated program namely, MSTAT.

Results and discussion

Effect of row arrangement

Results revealed that all the parameters studied were significantly influenced by row arrangement means spacing at all the dates of sampling. Plant height in all the row arrangements increased progressively with the advancement of time from 25 to 85 DAT. Double row arrangements had the tallest plant at all the dates of sampling. The highest plant height (115.84 cm) was recorded in double row arrangement at 85 DAT (Fig. 1). It was observed that at all the dates of samplings triple row produced the shortest plant might be due to high competition for light, space and nutrients among the plants. Number of total tillers hill⁻¹ was significantly influenced by row arrangement hill⁻¹ at 25 to 85 DAT (Fig. 2). Double row produced the highest number of total tillers than single and triple row at 45, 65, and 85 DAT. Leaf area differed significantly at all the DATs due to row arrangement. The result indicates that leaf area index increases with the increase in age of the plant up to 65 DAT and then declines (Fig. 3). It was found that a

double row produced the highest leaf area index (5.75) at 65 DAT. Total leaf area increased with increasing days due to row arrangement at 25 DAT up to 65 DAT and then declined at 85 DAT. The lowest leaf area index (4.26) was recorded at 75 DAT in triple row arrangement. Total dry matter production hill⁻¹ was significantly influenced by row arrangements at all dates of samplings. Results showed that the total dry matter accumulation increased with increase of time. At 25 DAT the highest dry matter production (3.83g) was obtained from double row arrangement whereas the lowest dry matter (3.08 g) was obtained from triple row arrangement. At 85 DAT the highest (35.88 g) dry matter production was obtained from double row arrangement whereas lowest dry matter (30.25 g) was obtained from triple row arrangement. (Fig. 4).

Fig. 1 Effect of row arrangement on plant height at different days after transplanting of aromatic fine rice cv. BRR1 dhan34

Fig. 2 Effect of row arrangement on number of total tillers hill⁻¹ at different days after transplanting of aromatic fine rice cv. BRR1

Fig. 3 Effect of row arrangement management on leaf area index (LAI) at different days after transplanting of aromatic fine rice cv. BRR1 dhan34

Fig. 4 Effect of row arrangement on dry matter production hill⁻¹ at different days after transplanting of aromatic fine rice cv. BRR1 dhan34

Significant effect was observed on crop growth rate from 25-45 DAT to 65-85 DAT. The crop growth rate initially started to increase with the advancement of time and reached a peak at 65-85 DAT (Table 1). The highest crop growth rate (30.47 g m⁻² day⁻¹) was obtained in the double row arrangement followed by single row (27.02 g m⁻² day⁻¹) at 65-85 DAT. The lowest crop growth rate (25.17 g m⁻² day⁻¹) was recorded in case of triple row arrangement at 60-75 DAT. Previous research experiment revealed that the plant height, total tillers number hill⁻¹, leaf area index (LAI) panicle length, spikelets number panicle⁻¹, total grains panicle⁻¹ were significantly affected by spacing and the widest spacing showed better results than narrower spacing [17, 18]. Optimum plant density play an important role which helps plants to uptake micro or macro-

nutrients from the soil, influences the availability of sunlight on leaf area which leads to increased plant photosynthesis and respiration, and shows a direct effect on the plant growth and yield [19, 6]

Table 1. Effect of row arrangement on crop growth rate ($\text{g m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$) of aromatic fine rice at different days after transplanting

Row arrangement	Crop growth rate ($\text{g m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$) DAT		
	25 – 45	45 – 65	65 – 85
Single row	8.60b	16.70b	27.02b
Double row	9.36a	18.66a	30.47a
Triple row	7.58c	16.27c	25.17c
Level of significance	**	**	**
CV (%)	4.54	5.63	6.29

In a column, figures with same letter(s) or without letter do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letter differ significantly as per DMRT.

** =Significant at 1% level of probability.

Effect of nutrient management

Plant height and total tillers hill^{-1} was significantly influenced by nutrient management irrespective of growth stages. It was found that treatment F₃ (75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + Cow dung @ 5 t ha^{-1}) produced the highest plant height (119.67 cm) and highest number of total tillers hill^{-1} (13.12) at 85 DAT followed by treatment F₅ (75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure @ 2.5 t ha^{-1}) at 85 DAT. The shortest plant (108.89 cm) and the lowest number of total tillers hill^{-1} (11.78) were obtained from control treatment (no manures and no fertilizers) at 85 DAT (Table 2). This trend of plant stature was observed at all the dates of samplings. The number of total tillers hill^{-1} increased with increasing days after transplanting up to 65 DAT due to application of different levels of fertilizers and manures. The highest number of total tillers hill^{-1} occurred due to the absorption of more nutrients, moisture and also for availability of more sunlight. Different nutrient management had a significant effect on leaf area index at all Sampling dates. It was observed that leaf area was the highest in treatment F₃ (75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + 50% cow dung), which was statistically identical to the treatment F₅ (75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + 50% Poultry Manure), (Fig. 5). The leaf area index increased with increasing days due to nutrient management at 25 DAT up to 65 DAT and then started to decline at 85 DAT probably due to leaf senescence at higher ages (Fig. 5). The lowest leaf area index (4.34) was recorded in treatment F₀ (control) at 85 DAT.

Table 2. Effect of nutrient management on plant height at different days after transplanting of aromatic fine rice cv. BRRI dhan34

Nutrient management	Plant height (cm) DAT				Number of total tillers hill ⁻¹ DAT				Crop growth rate (g m ⁻² day ⁻¹) DAT		
	25	45	65	85	25	45	65	85	25-45	45 – 65	65 – 85
F ₀	43.67c	68.00d	95.08d	108.89c	3.78b	5.89c	12.89c	11.78c	5.57f	10.79f	15.50f
F ₁	46.89b	75.89b	101.7c	112.11b	4.44ab	8.00b	13.13b	12.22b	9.03c	19.10c	33.28c
F ₂	45.11b	72.78c	100.33c	105.50d	4.67b	8.33b	14.67b	12.11b	7.97e	16.74e	22.30e
F ₃	48.00a	84.00a	108.78a	119.67a	5.89a	10.56a	15.56a	14.89a	12.11a	22.27a	41.85a
F ₄	45.67	73.33c	98.89c	110.00b	4.89b	8.89b	13.22b	12.56b	8.47d	18.45d	28.45d
F ₅	47.44a	85.11a	104.67b	116.5a	5.67a	9.78a	15.00a	13.12a	10.18b	20.63b	39.82b
CV%	5.20	4.20	5.34	6.58	4.50	6.28	4.96	5.47	4.99	3.60	4.35
Level of significance	**	*	**	**	**	**	**	NS	**	**	**

In a column, figures with same letter(s) or without letter do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letter differ significantly as per DMRT.

** =Significant at 1% level of probability.

F₀ = control (no manures and fertilizers),

F₁ = recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers (i.e 150, 100, 70, 60 and 10 kg ha⁻¹ of Urea, TSP, MoP, Gypsum and ZnSO₄ respectively)

F₂ = 50% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹,

F₃ = 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹,

F₄ = 50% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha⁻¹,

F₅ = 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha⁻¹.

Fig. 5 Effect of nutrient management on leaf area index (LAI) at different days after transplanting of aromatic fine rice cv. BRRI dhan34

Fig. 6 Effect of nutrient management on dry matter production hill⁻¹ at different days after transplanting of aromatic fine rice cv. BRRI dhan34

Here,

F₀ = control (no manures and fertilizers)

F₁ = recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers (i.e 150, 100, 70, 60 and 10 kg ha⁻¹ of Urea, TSP, MoP, Gypsum and ZnSO₄ respectively)

F₂ = 50% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹

F₃ = 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹

F₄ = 50% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha⁻¹

F₅ = 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha⁻¹.

Total dry matter production hill⁻¹ varied significantly due to nutrient management at all the dates of samplings. Total dry matter production hill⁻¹ increased progressively with the advancement of time from 25 DAT to 85 DAT due to nutrient management (Fig. 6). At 85 DAT, the highest total dry matter accumulation (39.94 g) was observed at treatment F3 (75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung @ 5

t ha⁻¹) followed by treatment F₅ (75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure @ 2.5 t ha⁻¹) and the lowest dry matter accumulation (28.18 g) was observed in treatment F₀ (no manures and fertilizers). Nutrient management had a significant effect on crop growth rate from 25-45 DAT to 65-85 DAT. Crop growth rate showed an increasing trend up to 65-85 DAT (Table 2). The highest crop growth rate (41.85 g m⁻² day⁻¹) was produced in treatment F₃ (75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹) followed by F₅ (75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha⁻¹) and the lowest crop growth rate (15.50 g m⁻² day⁻¹) was recorded in treatment F₀ (control) at 65-85 DAT. Similar results were reported by [Shaha et al 2014](#). [20] The effects of combined use of cowdung and inorganic fertilizer showed significant results on growth, development, and yield of rice in field conditions [20]. [Mishra et al 2003](#) also reported that integrated application of organic manures and inorganic fertilizers has significant effectiveness for enhancing vegetative growth, development and yield of rice [21].

Effect of interaction of row arrangement and nutrient management

The results showed that among interaction the effect of row arrangement and level of nutrient management on plant height was significant at all the dates of samplings (Table 3). It was observed that the tallest plant stature (125.0 cm) was at 85 DAT in double row arrangement × 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung @ 5 t ha⁻¹ (R₂ × F₃) and the shortest plant stature (101.7 cm) was in triple row arrangement × no application of manures and fertilizers (R₃ × F₀). Number of total tillers hill⁻¹ had significant influence at 25 and 45 DAT by the interaction of row arrangements and combined level of poultry manure and inorganic fertilizers (Table 3). At 25 DAT, the highest number of total tillers hill⁻¹ (6.47) was observed in double row with 75% recommended dose of inorganic fertilizer + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹ (R₂ × F₃) and the lowest one (4.00) was obtained from triple row with control treatment (R₃ × F₀). At 65 DAT, the highest number of total tillers hill⁻¹ (16.20) was observed in double row with 75% Recommended dose of inorganic fertilizer with cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹ (R₂ × F₃), which was statistically identical to single row with 75% recommended dose of inorganic fertilizer with cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹ (R₁ × F₃). It was noticed that at all dates of sampling the lowest numbers of tillers were obtained from the triple row with control treatment (R₃ × F₀). It might be due to high competition for light, space and nutrients among the plants and lack of nutrients. The interaction between row arrangement and level of nutrient management had a significant effect on leaf area index at all the DAT at 1% level of probability (Table 3). The interaction of double row arrangement × 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹ produced the highest the leaf area index (6.40) at 65 DAT. The leaf area index was increased with increasing days after transplanting up to 65 DAT due to row arrangement and application of different levels of fertilizers and manures at 25 DAT up to 65 DAT. This might be resulting from potentiality of double row arrangement and influence of nutrients. After 65 DAT leaf area

index started to decline for all interactions. The second highest leaf area was produced from interaction of single row arrangement \times 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung @ 5 t ha⁻¹. The lowest leaf area index was recorded (3.38) in the interaction of triple row arrangement \times Control (no manures and fertilizers) at the 85 DAT. Total dry matter was significantly influenced at all the dates of samplings by the interaction of row arrangements and nutrient management. Total dry matter increased progressively with the advancement of time due to row arrangements and nutrient management at 25 DAT up to 85 DAT. At 25 DAT, the highest total dry matter plant⁻¹ (5.03 g) was observed in a double row with recommended dose of inorganic fertilizer (R₂ \times F₁). At 85 DAT, the highest total dry matter (61.09 g) was observed in double row with 75% Recommended dose of inorganic fertilizer + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹ (R₂ \times F₃) which was statistically identical to double row with 75% Recommended dose of inorganic fertilizer + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha⁻¹ (R₂ \times F₅) and double row with recommended dose of inorganic fertilizer (R₂ \times F₁) whereas the lowest one (32.07 g) was obtained from triple row with control treatment (R₃ \times F₀) which was statistically identical to single row with control treatment (R₁ \times F₀) (Table 4). The interaction effect of row arrangement and level of nutrient management on crop growth rate was significant at all DATs (Table 4). It was observed that the highest crop growth rate (46.96 g m⁻² day⁻¹) was observed in case of interaction between double row arrangement and 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹ (R₂ \times F₃) at 65-85 DAT followed by double row arrangement and 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha⁻¹ (R₂ \times F₅). The lowest crop growth rate (15.35 g m⁻² day⁻¹) was observed due to interaction between triple row arrangement \times control, which was statistically identical with R₁ \times F₀. Similar results was reported by [Sharkar et al 2014](#), [Melkie et al 2020](#) [5, 22]. [Sharkar et al 2014](#) observed that application of combined with 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + 50% cowdung in terms of yield components and yield of aromatic fine rice cv. BRRI dhan34 [5]. [Melkie et al 2020](#) also found that the number of total tillers m⁻², number of effective tillers per 0.5 m row length, 1000 grain weights, biomass yield, straw yield and harvesting index were highly significant at (P<0.01) and grain yield was significant at (P<0.05) which influenced by the interaction effect of variety, row spacing and Nitrogen levels [22].

Table 3 Effect of interaction of row arrangement and nutrient management on plant height, number of total tillers hill⁻¹, leaf area index (LAI) at different days after transplanting

Row arrangement × Nutrient management	Plant height (cm)			Number of total tillers hill ⁻¹			Leaf area index (LAI)		
	25	45	85	25	45	85	25	45	85
R ₁ × F ₀	43.40jk	60.07mn	106.4m	4.07kl	6.53lm	11.77l	0.980l	1.73i	3.75m
R ₁ × F ₁	47.20	72.47def	115.8def	4.73ef	7.87def	13.90de	1.39de	2.44c	5.35ef
R ₁ × F ₂	45.80ef	67.33ijk	114.0efgh	4.53fgh	7.67efg	13.20gh	1.28gh	2.18ef	5.12ghi
R ₁ × F ₃	49.13ab	81.93b	122.2b	5.27b	8.33bc	14.77b	1.60ab	2.70b	6.05b
R ₁ × F ₄	45.87ef	69.00ghij	114.0fghi	4.67fg	7.73ef	13.53ef	1.33ef	2.19de	5.30fg
R ₁ × F ₅	47.60c	77.00c	117.4cd	5.00cd	8.13cd	13.93de	1.45cd	2.52c	5.54de
R ₂ × F ₀	43.60ij	67.40ijk	110.5jkl	4.33hij	6.93jk	12.03kl	1.17jk	1.78i	3.87m
R ₂ × F ₁	47.33cd	76.27cd	115.8def	5.13bcd	8.60b	13.90de	1.47c	2.47c	5.75c
R ₂ × F ₂	46.20de	72.27def	114.3defg	4.60fgh	7.67efg	13.70de	1.39de	2.24de	5.50de
R ₂ × F ₃	50.13a	92.0a	125.0a	6.47a	9.13a	15.60a	1.67a	2.85a	6.40a
R ₂ × F ₄	46.27de	73.53cdef	115.2defg	5.00cd	7.87def	13.83de	1.39cd	2.31d	5.52de
R ₂ × F ₅	48.20	77.33c	120.1bc	5.20bc	8.67b	14.37c	1.55b	2.68b	6.18b
R ₃ × F ₀	42.27l	59.80n	101.7n	4.00l	6.40m	11.37m	0.87m	1.54j	3.38n
R ₃ × F ₁	45.33ef	70.53fghi	114.0efgh	4.47fgh	7.80def	13.53ef	1.30fg	2.10fg	5.26fgh
R ₃ × F ₂	44.07gh	67.27ijk	112.5fghi	4.33hij	7.07ijk	12.57ij	1.21ijk	1.99gh	4.95jk
R ₃ × F ₃	45.87ef	75.07cde	120.6b	5.20bc	7.97de	14.07cd	1.55b	2.44c	5.70cd
R ₃ × F ₄	45.87ef	69.00ghij	114.0fghi	4.40ghi	7.53fgh	13.37fg	1.29fg	2.09fg	5.07hij
R ₃ × F ₅	47.60c	77.00c	117.4cd	4.93de	7.87def	13.67de	1.37de	2.44c	3.75m
CV (%)	5.20	4.28	4.58	3.08	2.69	1.45	3.61	3.55	2.18
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	*	*	*	*	**

In a column, figures with same letter(s) or without letter do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letter differ significantly as per DMRT.

** = Significant at 1% level of probability.

* = Significant at 5% level of probability.

R₁ = Single row arrangement, R₂ = Double row arrangement, R₃ = Triple row arrangement.

F₀ = control (no manures and fertilizers), F₁ = recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers (i.e 150, 100, 70, 60 and 10 kg ha⁻¹ of Urea, TSP, MoP, Gypsum and ZnSO₄ respectively)

F₂ = 50% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹,

F₃ = 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha⁻¹,

F₄ = 50% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha⁻¹,

F₅ = 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha⁻¹.

Table 4. Effect of interaction of row arrangement and nutrient management on total dry matter production hill^{-1} (g) and crop growth rate ($\text{g m}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$) at different days after transplanting

Row arrangement × Nutrient management	Total dry matter production hill^{-1} (g)				Crop growth rate ($\text{g m}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$)			
	25	45	65	85	25 – 45	45 – 65	65 – 85	85 – 105
$R_1 \times F_0$	2.25i	6.46i	20.43j	32.88i	6.15i	10.55p	16.63k	16.63k
$R_1 \times F_1$	3.82b	8.68cde	35.57d	51.53c	9.11cd	18.68fgh	31.16e	31.16e
$R_1 \times F_2$	2.83fg	8.33defg	26.53f	43.78ef	7.92efg	16.83jkl	22.32h	22.32h
$R_1 \times F_3$	4.01b	9.80b	40.10b	59.48a	11.32b	21.31c	40.68c	40.68c
$R_1 \times F_4$	3.58c	8.62cde	32.00e	48.45cd	8.58de	18.12hi	27.50f	27.50f
$R_1 \times F_5$	3.95b	8.88cd	38.55bc	55.48b	10.98b	19.64ef	38.49d	38.49d
$R_2 \times F_0$	2.47hi	6.47i	20.85j	34.15g	6.32i	12.65o	17.2k	17.2k
$R_2 \times F_1$	5.03a	8.73cde	40.66b	59.85a	9.77c	20.20de	37.58d	37.58d
$R_2 \times F_2$	3.15e	8.33defg	26.70f	47.10d	8.58de	17.28ijk	24.66g	24.66g
$R_2 \times F_3$	3.91b	11.06a	43.32a	61.09a	15.27a	24.72a	46.96a	46.96a
$R_2 \times F_4$	3.81b	8.64cde	32.16e	49.64cd	8.62de	19.38efg	30.81e	30.81e
$R_2 \times F_5$	4.03b	9.16c	43.23a	60.02a	11.15b	22.88b	43.76b	43.76b
$R_3 \times F_0$	1.85j	6.34i	20.94j	32.07i	4.25j	9.16q	12.66l	12.66l
$R_3 \times F_1$	3.20de	7.86ghi	33.06de	50.49c	8.23ef	18.42gh	31.09e	31.09e
$R_3 \times F_2$	2.63gh	7.25jk	26.06fg	41.81fg	7.43gh	16.10lmn	19.93ij	19.93ij
$R_3 \times F_3$	3.90b	8.44def	39.44b	55.15b	9.73c	20.79cd	37.32d	37.32d
$R_3 \times F_4$	3.58c	8.62cde	32.00e	48.45cd	8.22ef	17.85hij	27.05f	27.05f
$R_3 \times F_5$	3.95b	8.88cd	39.55bc	55.48b	8.42de	19.38efg	37.21d	37.21d
CV (%)	4.30	4.85	4.02	3.9	4.99	3.60	4.35	4.35
Level of significance	**	*	**	**	**	**	**	**

In a column, figures with same letter(s) or without letter do not differ significantly whereas figures with dissimilar letter differ significantly as per DMRT.

** = Significant at 1% level of probability.

* = Significant at 5% level of probability.

R_1 = Single row arrangement, R_2 = Double row arrangement, R_3 = Triple row arrangement.

F_0 = control (no manures and fertilizers), F_1 = recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers (i.e 150, 100, 70, 60 and 10 kg ha^{-1} of Urea, TSP, MoP, Gypsum and ZnSO_4 respectively)

F_2 = 50% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha^{-1} ,

F_3 = 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha^{-1} ,

F_4 = 50% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha^{-1} ,

F_5 = 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha^{-1} .

Conclusion

The conclusion drawn from the study, row arrangement and nutrient management has significantly affected the growth of aromatic fine rice cv. BRR1 dhan34. Double row arrangement combined with 75% recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + cow dung at 5 t ha^{-1} and 75% of recommended dose of inorganic fertilizers + poultry manure at 2.5 t ha^{-1} appeared as the promising practice in aromatic fine rice cv. BRR1 dhan34 cultivation in terms of growth. The result also indicates the potential use of organic

manures combined with inorganic fertilizers could be reduced the use of inorganic fertilizers as well as chemicals without decreasing the growth and yield of rice. However, further detailed studies are to be carried out to arrive at a concrete decision.

References

1. Singh Y, Singh US. Genetic diversity analysis in aromatic rice germplasm using agro- morphological traits. *Indian Journal of Plant Genetic Resources*. 2008; 21(1): 32-37.
2. BBS (Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics). *The Yearbook of Agricultural Statistics of Bangladesh*. Statistics Division, Ministry of Planning. Government of the peoples Republic of Bangladesh. Dhaka. Bangladesh. 2016; 56-65.
3. Giraud G. *The World Market of Fragrant Rice, Main Issues and Perspectives* International Food and Agribusiness Management Association. 2013;16(2):1-20.
4. Howe CW, Lazo JK, Weber KR. The economic impacts of agriculture-to-urban water transfers on the area of origin: a case study of the Arkansas River Valley in Colorado. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*: 1990;72 (5):1200-1204.
5. Sarkar S K, Sarkar MAR, Islam N, Paul SK. Yield and quality of aromatic fine rice as affected by variety and nutrient management. *Journal of Bangladesh Agricultural University*. 2014;12(2):279–284.
6. Islam MS, Najnine F, Khaton MA, Uddin MR. Effect of Date of Transplanting and Spacing under Raised Bed System on the Yield of Superamandhan. *North American Academic Research*. 2021;4(9):152-165.
7. Naznine F, Hossain I, Akter M. Investigation on quality and management of wheat seed in Bogra and Naogaon. *Progressive Agriculture*. 2016;27(2):101–109.
8. Adhikari A, Sarkar MAR, Paul SK, Saha KK. Impact of nutrient management on the yield performance of some aromatic fine rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) varieties in Boro season. *Archives of Agriculture and Environmental Science*. 2018; 3(3):245-251.
9. BRRI (Bangladesh Rice Research Institute). *Annual Report for 1991 Bangladesh Rice Research Institute* Joydebpur, Gazipur. 1991;3-5.
10. Hossain SMA, Salam MU, Islam MS. Effect of alternate row spacings on rice yield in relation to rice-fish culture. *International Journal of Tropical Agriculture*. 1990;6: 1-5.

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11. Sarkar MAR, Paul SK, Hossain MA. Effect of row arrangements, age of tiller seedling and number of seedlings hill on performance of transplant aman rice. *Journal of Agricultural Science*. 2011;6(2):59-68.
 12. Rahman M M, Yakupitiyage A. Use of fishpond sediment for sustainable aquaculture-agriculture farming. *International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning*. 2006;1: 192-202.
 13. Bhuiyan NI. Crop production trends and need of sustainability in Agriculture. Paper presented at the workshop, Integrated Nutrient Management for Sustainable Agriculture, Held at Dhaka, Bangladesh. 1994;26-28.
 14. BRRI (Bangladesh Rice Research Institute). Annual Report for 1988. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Gazipur. 1990;08-14.
 15. Hunt R. The fitted curve in plant growth studies. In: *Math and Plant Physiology* (Eds. D. A. Rose and D. A. C. Edwas). Aca. Press. 1978.
 16. Gomez KA, Gomez AA. Statistical procedure for agricultural research. International Rice Research Institute, Philippines, John Wiley and Sons. New York, Chichester, Brisbane, Toronto, Singapore. 1984;680.
 17. Mirza H, Kamrunt N, Roy TS, Rahman ML, Hossain MZ, Ahmed JU. Tiller dynamics and dry matter production of transplanted rice as affected by plant spacing and number of seedlings per hill. *Academic Journal of Plant Sciences*. 2009;2(3):162-168.
 18. Ogbodo EN, Ekpe II, Utobo EB, Ogah EO. Effect of plant spacing and nitrogen rates on the growth and yield of rice at Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Southeast Nigeria. *Research Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences*. 2010;6(5):653-658.
 19. Rao KS, Moorthy BTS. Hybrid rice technology for achieved higher yield during dry season in coastal Orissa. *Indian Farm*. 2003;53(3):4-5.
 20. Shaha U, Bhuiya MSU, Paul SK. Integrated use of cowdung and inorganic fertilizer on the performance of modern varieties of transplanted aman rice. *Journal of Agroforestry and Environment*. 2014;8(2): 81-84.
 21. Mishra OT, Tomar VS, Shamar RA, Rajput AM. Response of Rice to organic and inorganic fertilizers. *Crop Research*. 2003;9(2):233-237.
 22. Melkie Z, Belete K, Takele A. Effect of Nitrogen Fertilizer Levels and Row Spacing on Yield and Yield Components of Upland Rice Varieties in Pawe, Northwestern Ethiopia. *Journal of Natural Sciences Research*. 2020; 10(11):1-12.

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